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Analysis of Production Growth and Sales of Motor Vehicles in Uzbekistan

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***Abstract:** It is known that the production of motor vehicles in Uzbekistan has been developing rapidly in recent years.*

The article presents the results of research on the growth of the production of automobile vehicles in the Republic of Uzbekistan and their production.

***Key words:** motor vehicle, production of cars, sales of motor vehicles, passenger cars, individuals.*

Introduction

Currently, it is impossible to imagine modern life without road transport. The number of cars is growing every year, but, unfortunately, the number of road accidents is also growing. Road traffic accidents caused by drivers account for the majority of all accidents.

Drivers' ability to prevent traffic accidents depends on their level of preparedness. Driving a car requires the driver to make decisions in a rapidly changing environment. With a constant lack of time, the driver cannot conduct a detailed analysis of all possible options for action and take into account their consequences, as well as consult with someone about the correctness of the chosen decision. Improving the driver training system (from initial to workshop) significantly contributes to improving road safety [1].

During the training process, a set of knowledge, abilities, skills and qualities are formed that guarantee reliable operation in the process of practical driving.

Due to the unprecedented growth in the number of vehicles in Uzbekistan and at the same time a serious lag in the development of the corresponding road infrastructure, the task of ensuring road safety comes to the fore [2].

A new report from KPMG Uzbekistan provides an analysis of the Uzbekistan vehicle market, revealing significant potential for growth in the automotive sector. KPMG is one of the world's largest networks of professional firms providing audit, tax, legal and advisory services. KPMG has offices in 143 countries and employs more than 270 thousand employees worldwide. KPMG Caucasus and Central Asia unites offices in Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Armenia, Georgia and Azerbaijan. The name "KPMG" stands for "Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler" [3].

The results of an analysis carried out by this company in 2023 showed that in Uzbekistan the number of cars per 1000 people is 103 cars.

Despite the fact that this figure is lower than in other countries: (Kazakhstan - 220; Turkey - 175.7; Belarus - 330 and Russia - 327 cars) it creates serious problems in ensuring road safety.

This indicates significant growth potential in the automotive market. According to KPMG experts, the gap between Uzbekistan and other countries may be narrowing and the demand for cars in the country will increase as the economic situation further improves and household incomes grow. On the other hand, the level of population demand for cars in Uzbekistan is also influenced by the availability of financial resources.

At the end of last year, the majority of cars were sold for personal purposes [4]:

- individuals and households for personal purposes - 3.4 million cars;
- individuals and households for commercial purposes - 481 thousand cars;
- legal entities for official use - 284 thousand cars;
- legal entities for commercial purposes - 28 thousand cars;
- ministries and departments - 13 thousand cars.

Most cars were purchased through direct purchase:

- through direct purchase - 1.2 million cars;
- on credit/leasing - 295 thousand cars;
- other methods - 94 thousand cars.

The development of the car market in Uzbekistan is closely related to the improvement of the economic well-being of the population, which stimulates demand for personal cars and supports the growth of sales in the country's automobile industry.

2023 saw significant growth in new car sales, up 33% from the previous year. This indicates increased demand for new cars.

An increase in sales of domestic and foreign car brands is also observed against the backdrop of a reduction in customs duties.

The automobile market of Uzbekistan is experiencing significant changes. In recent years, the country has demonstrated steady growth in the production and import of passenger cars, and is also actively developing new projects in the production of electric vehicles. The conducted research aims not only to analyze the current state of the market, but also to predict its development until 2030, based on modeling of three scenarios: targeted, dynamic and conservative.

One of the main objectives of the study is to analyze the relationships between participants in the automotive market of Uzbekistan and identify key factors that will influence its further development.

For this purpose, data from open sources, interviews with market players, as well as econometric and statistical methods are used to better understand the processes occurring in this area.

During the study, modeling was used based on three development scenarios [4]:

- the targeted scenario focuses on active government regulation and support for the automotive industry;
- the dynamic scenario assumes the development of the market, taking into account market factors, such as growth in household incomes and the introduction of new technologies;
- the conservative scenario takes into account possible external and internal risks, including global economic and political challenges.

The results of the analysis confirm that in the period from 2020 to 2024, the Uzbekistan market showed significant growth. In 2023, 456 thousand cars were sold, of which 380 thousand were produced domestically. At the same time, imports of passenger cars also increased: over the past year, its volume more than doubled compared to 2022 and amounted to 73 thousand units. Moreover, the active development of the online car trading market was revealed. New platforms for purchasing cars have emerged, such as Uzum Auto and Alif.

The growth of the automotive sector in Uzbekistan is associated with a number of factors. These include rising incomes, improving infrastructure, and increasing government support for the automobile industry. The spread of electric vehicles and the introduction of “green” technologies are also becoming significant factors. This suggests that the automotive industry will actively develop in the coming years.

Imports of cars continue to grow, due to increased demand for new models and a variety of choices. However, local production remains a key driver of growth, and the emergence of new factories only further confirms this trend.

In August 2024, sales of passenger cars increased by 11% to 102 thousand units, which is the highest value since February of that year [5].

Conclusion

The results of a study of the automobile market of Uzbekistan show that the country continues to successfully develop its automobile industry, despite global challenges. The key factors for market growth remain the development of domestic production, increased imports and the introduction of new technologies, such as electric vehicles.

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